

Title: Sleep Apnea, Hypoxia, and Pain

Authors: Elissaios Karageorgiou, MD PhD¹, Athanasia Giannopoulou, MD¹, Klimentini E. Karageorgiou, MD PhD², Anthony G. Doufas, MD, PhD³

1. Sleep & Memory Center, Neurological Institute of Athens, Greece
2. Center for Multiple Sclerosis and Autoimmune Disorders, Neurological Institute of Athens, Greece
3. Department of Anesthesiology, Perioperative and Pain Medicine, Stanford University School of Medicine, USA

Corresponding author:

Elissaios Karageorgiou, MD PhD

Sleep & Memory Center,

Neurological Institute of Athens

2 Vas. Alexandrou Ave, 11634, Athens, Greece

Email: e.karageorgiou@nioa.gr

Tel: +30-210-7217-457

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Abstract

Purpose of review: We examined the relationship between sleep apnea and hypoxia, jointly defined as sleep-related breathing disorders (SRBD), and pain, seeking to answer (a) whether SRBD are associated with specific pain phenotypes and pathophysiologies, and (b) whether pain syndromes are associated with specific SRBD. Finally, (c) we reviewed treatment opportunities at their interface.

Recent findings: Individuals with SRBD are 3-4 times more likely to suffer from tension type or morning headache, chronic widespread pain, or temporomandibular disorder. Two mechanisms explain how SRBD might lead to pain: (i) Sleep fragmentation and deprivation, and (ii) SRBD-associated hypoxia-hypercapnia. Treating SRBD improves chronic pain by 38-92%. Instead, there are no case-control studies supporting pain as a risk factor for SRBD. Finally, opioid use is primarily associated with obstructive, rather than central, apnea, likely through central inhibition of hypoglossal nerve activity.

Summary: Clinicians should inquire for co-existence of pain and SRBD symptoms, especially since SRBD therapy improves pain. Optimal results are achieved through prolonged compliance of targeted positive airway pressure / non-invasive ventilation therapy. Findings also inform future research towards novel therapies for pain across SRBD-associated mechanisms of hypoxia-hypercapnia and sleep fragmentation and deprivation.

Introduction

In this review, we examine the latest evidence on the clinicopathological relationship between sleep-related breathing disorders (SRBD) (1), as represented through sleep apnea and sleep-related hypoxia, and pain syndromes. In that vein, we review current research investigating whether (a) SRBD and its consequences are associated with specific pain phenotypes and their pathophysiological mechanisms, as well as whether (b) pain syndromes and their treatments are associated with specific SRBD phenotypes. Finally, we examine the evidence on (c) treatment opportunities at the interface between SRBD and pain. As we describe below, despite a general tendency in recent years for presenting relationships between syndromes or pathologies in a balanced, bidirectional manner, current evidence mainly supports a unidirectional causal relationship between SRBD and pain syndromes, with pathophysiological processes involved in SRBD primarily activating those that give rise to pain.

In defining these two entities, SRBD are characterized by abnormalities of respiration during sleep (1), resulting in impaired gas exchange and dysregulation of the homeostatic and dynamic sleep processes through feedforward and feedback pathways. SRBD can be clustered in two main groups: (a) Sleep Apnea Syndromes, which are defined based on the causal pathways that lead to SRBD, and (b) Hypoventilation and Hypoxemia Syndromes, which are defined according to specific biological outcomes of SRBD (i.e., elevated arterial tension of carbon dioxide). Sleep Apnea Syndromes are organized according to functional features into (i) Obstructive, where there are episodes of complete or partial upper airway obstruction, and (ii) Central, where there is reduction or cessation of airflow due to decreased respiratory effort. In turn, Hypoventilation and Hypoxemia Syndromes are subdivided according to their specific pathological causes (i.e., obesity, central nervous system dysfunction, medical disorder, medication or substance use or abuse, and idiopathic) (1).

The other entity of the discussed relationship, bodily pain, is a multimodal percept defined as an unpleasant somatosensory experience integrating sensory, cognitive, and emotional processes through precise spatiotemporal dynamics of the respective brain networks from which the pain percept arises (**Figure 1**) (2). In this review, we specifically focus on chronic rather than acute pain syndromes, because they have more impact on quality of life and a clearer association to SRBD. Current international classification criteria of chronic pain conceptually separate primary pain, where a specific pathophysiology is unclear, from pain where a medical or pathophysiological cause is known. The latter is subdivided according to (a) the location from where the pain arises (headache and orofacial, visceral), (b) its pathophysiology (neuropathic, musculoskeletal), and (c) its cause (cancer, postsurgical, and post-traumatic) (3).

In what follows, we discuss the observed associations between SRBD and Pain syndromes, and highlight known or plausible pathophysiological pathways that link the two. We approach the potential causal relationships serially, first considering SRBD as the precondition and Pain syndromes as the outcome, and then reversing this directionality. That said, most human studies in the field follow cross-sectional or cohort observational designs, and thus a true cause-and-effect relationship cannot be formally verified. Instead, intervention trials of provoking one condition (e.g., SRBD or chronic pain) to see outcomes in the other can test for causal relationships, but are implemented primarily in animal models using indirect markers of pain and are few, therefore being insufficient for definitive clinical answers. Furthermore, most studies that address issues of sleep disorders and pain focus on insomnia phenotypes or non-specific sleep quality metrics, rather than SRBD specifically. Nonetheless, there is growing converging evidence that helps us better comprehend the relationship between SRBD and pain towards specific clinical decisions.

Observational associations between SRBD and Pain Syndromes

Most studies that have examined the prevalence of SRBD and Pain Syndromes are relying primarily on sleep clinic cohorts, and focus on people with known SRBD and coexistent pain syndromes (**Table 1**). Overall, one-in-seven to one-in-three people who have SRBD also present with a painful symptom or suffer from a pain disorder. This prevalence is lower when strict diagnostic criteria are used in establishing a pain diagnosis, compared to self-reported pain, which can be either a result of patients over-reporting pain to enhance provider responsiveness and to their fear of disease, or, instead, due to clinicians underappreciating patient-reported pain severity (4,5). More specifically, the most common primary pain syndromes studied based on diagnostic criteria are headache disorders, chronic widespread pain (CWP), and temporomandibular disorder (TMD), with headache often showing a larger prevalence than the rest, although a large variability exists between studies, likely the result of access to different populations. Certain studies that examined whether the presence of SRBD is associated with higher likelihood of specific pain syndromes diagnoses, found that the presence of SRBD makes it more likely for people to have a primary pain syndrome, especially tension type headache (TTH), morning headache, CWP, and TMD (6–14), but was not more likely in people with migraine or people with a somatoform disorder (15,16), suggesting a musculoskeletal component in the development of pain in SRBD. Overall, people with SRBD are three to four times more likely to have one of the above pain syndromes. In addition, although the presence of postoperative pain was similar between people with SRBD and those without, it has been easier to manage postoperative pain if people were compliant with their positive airway pressure (PAP) / non-invasive ventilation (NIV) treatment modality (17). Finally, the presence of SRBD has been shown to worsen pain tolerance by about 10-30% across studies (18,19).

Examining the inverse relationship in people with various types of pain syndromes and how these might affect SRBD prevalence (**Table 2**), studies reveal that the latter is often not significantly different between patients with pain syndromes and controls, in head-to-head group comparisons (20–24). Interestingly, in one study, the prevalence of SRBD was found to be even lower in patients with

headache compared to controls (20). Regarding pediatric populations, the presence of TTH in a small sample was not associated with SRBD. Instead, higher prevalence of SRBD has been observed in pediatric migraine, where 40-49% of children with migraine had SRBD compared to the anticipated 3% in the general population (25–27). However, this finding does not support a causal pathway from migraine to SRBD, since it is not the result of a case-control study, nor is there an evident pathophysiological mechanism. Instead, it may reflect a selection bias of children presenting in clinic, since patients with migraine tend to be more susceptible to hypoxemia (28), and, thus, children with comorbid SRBD are more likely to present in clinic. An interesting finding with a possible pathophysiological element is the case of TMD, where, although apnea and hypopnea severity were not different between groups, Respiratory Effort Related Arousals (RERAs) were twice as common in people with TMD (21). This may be explained as more effortful breathing in people with TMD, which can inform sleep physicians on the need to assess for RERAs and consider more tailored interventions. Furthermore, there is a strong correlation in both sexes between CWP and SRBD, especially Obstructive Sleep Apnea (OSA). Review of results comparing middle-aged men and women, indicated that men with CWP were twice as likely to have SRBD compared to women (29,30). This discrepancy may be explained by a difference in overall SRBD prevalence before and after menopause, a confounder that has not been accounted for in existing studies (29,30). Even though there are no prospective studies to allow for causal inference, it is unlikely that pain syndromes themselves lead to SRBD emergence. Instead, sequelae of pain possibly explain this association.

One possible pathophysiological pathway to explain the above is the use of central nervous system depressant medications in patients with chronic pain (**Table 3**), especially in CWP where 58.2% of patients are on opioids (31). Studies in people with chronic opioid use for pain syndromes verify an association with SRBD, identifying OSA in 14-39% and hypoxia in 8-10% of chronic opioid users (32–34) while OSA severity was higher in those who use opioids compared to non-users. Instead, and against

what has been observed in patients without pain who are on chronic opioid use (35,36), central apneas were not significantly more frequent in a double-blind placebo-controlled study in people with pain syndromes on chronic opioids (37). Additionally, results from only two studies identified an increased prevalence of CSA in chronic opioid users with pain syndromes, but even in these samples, OSA was 30-60% more prevalent than CSA. The increased OSA in chronic opioid use can be explained through central mechanisms inhibiting hypoglossal nerve activity rather than any peripheral neuromuscular junction effects (38,39). The lack of increased CSA across most studies, despite the known depressive central effects of opioids on respiratory drive (40), can be explained by sample differences, where for example patients with certain pain syndromes have an increased sympathetic breathing drive, or have variable opioid dosing.

In summary, the above prospective and retrospective studies inform us that SRBD are more likely to be causal to pain syndromes and not the opposite, especially for TTH, CWP, and TMD. They also highlight for clinicians the importance of inquiring about pain symptoms in sleep clinics as outcomes of interest, as well as SRBD-related symptoms in pain clinics for pursuing diagnostic testing and treatments that may also improve pain outcomes. Also, conventional treatment with PAP/NIV, rather than servo-ventilation, may be sufficient in people on chronic opioid use, since they more frequently suffer from OSA than CSA. Finally, although these results support SRBD provoking or exacerbating pain syndromes, they do not indicate which specific pathophysiological pathways are involved.

Pathophysiological implications of sleep-related breathing disorders on pain pathways and syndromes

The experience of bodily pain involves the activation of various neural pathways and networks. Pain pathways transmit somatosensory information from peripheral nociceptors of lightly myelinated medium diameter A δ fibers and unmyelinated small diameter C fibers to the cortical pain matrix via spinal, reticular formation, and thalamic relay stations. It is at the cortical level where the pain matrix,

through its somatosensory, cognitive, and emotional networks, serves in the multimodal perception of pain (**Figure 1**) (2,41–44). Chronic pain arises from sensitization of either peripheral or central pain pathways. Peripheral sensitization is associated with prolonged nociceptor excitability and leads to hyper-responsiveness to somatosensory stimuli (noxious or innocuous), whereas central sensitization is associated with an amplification of responses to ascending pain pathways (e.g., via NMDA receptors) (45) and central pain matrix networks (42). Central sensitization explains the emotional and cognitive maladaptive responses observed in chronic pain, in addition to somatosensory amplified responses. In general, chronic pain mechanisms of hyperalgesia, including allodynia, pain spread, and referral, are proven to involve both central and peripheral sensitization (46,47). To that end, pathophysiological effects of SRBD can modulate both peripheral and central pain-related mechanisms, explaining the clinically observed relationships between SRBD and pain.

There are two main hypotheses on how SRBD can lead to pain (**Figure 2**). The first involves sleep-related hypoxia-hypercapnia as triggers for pain induction and chronic pain modulation. Studies in animal models indicate that hypoxia can activate certain pain receptors, such as Transient receptor potential cation channel (TRP), subfamily A member 1 (TRPA1) and TRP subfamily V member 1 (TRPV1), leading to increased pain sensitivity and painful dysesthesia (48). This effect is thought to be mediated through the release of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and the activation of hypoxia-inducible factor 1 α (HIF-1 α), a transcription factor that regulates cellular response to hypoxia (8,49). Additionally, nocturnal hypoxia is linked to increased expression of proinflammatory cytokines, such as interleukin 6 (IL-6) and tumor necrosis factor α (TNF- α) (50). IL-6 trans-signaling can lead to an upregulation of neurotransmission-related proteins, such as TRPV1 and TRPV member 2 (TRPV2), and result in the activation of primary afferent sensory neurons (51,52). The TNF- α – TNF Receptor 1 complex is suggested to activate protein kinase C ϵ mediated hyperalgesic priming, which leads to sensitization of primary afferent nociceptors

(53). Sympathetic nervous system activation due to chemoreflex and baroreflex dysfunction, as a result of hypoxemia, could further explain an elevation of interleukin concentrations (54).

Similarly, hypercapnia has also been proposed to provoke oxidative stress (55) that could be a mechanism leading to pain. However, in many studies, hypercapnia exhibits anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties. There is evidence suggesting that hypercapnia decreases the expression of IL-6, IL-8 and TNF- α (56) and elevates human pain thresholds (57). In fact, moderate and severe hypercapnia in animal models preferentially suppresses synaptic transmission of sensory pathways, through a mechanism mediated by endogenous opioids, both in spinal and supraspinal sites (58). On a network level, hypercapnia can lead to depression of activity in cortical centers of the pain matrix, thus attenuating their activity as a response to painful percepts (59). Finally, an alternative common mechanism involves cerebral vasodilation caused by both hypoxia and hypercapnia, which in turn leads to elevated intracranial pressure (ICP) and headache (60,61). The above might partially explain the findings observed in studies on morning headaches, where it has been hypothesized that disordered gas exchange from SRBD is causal to pain. Overall, however, objective PSG metrics indicate that hypoxia severity is only mildly worse in people with morning headaches (82.7% vs. 84.9% average SpO₂; 79.6% vs 82.7% REM min SpO₂) [5]. Similar results were found in a different study where patients with OSA and headache had significantly lower SaO₂ values (82.5% \pm 6.8) compared to those without headache (86.1% \pm 5.3, p<0.03) (62). The inverse, albeit not significant, is observed in another study, where AHI severity was worse in people with OSA who did not have pain (N = 90) compared to those with chronic pain (N = 55) (32.8 vs. 19.7; p = 0.08), whereas sleep hypoxemia was not predictive of pain (min SpO₂ 81.5% vs. 84.0%; p = 0.42) [6]. An intra-individual polysomnographic comparison between nights with and without morning tension type headaches did not reveal any association to average SaO₂ or AHI (9). Similar results have been found for minimum and average SaO₂, as well as total sleep time SaO₂ <90% in an independent study after adjusting for clinical comorbidities, sleep fragmentation, and systemic

inflammation (8). However, all three metrics were significantly associated with an increase of a composite pain score combining morning headache, headache disrupting sleep, chest pain while in bed, and pain disrupting sleep, even after adjusting for confounders (8). Collectively, the above findings raise the possibility that SRBD-associated hypoxia-hypercapnia may exacerbate pain acutely, but allows for decreased responsiveness to pain in the long term.

The second pathophysiological theory associating SRBD to pain involves effects of sleep fragmentation and sleep deprivation, which are common in SRBD (50,63). Analyses of fMRI data revealed that sleep deprivation increased the primary somatosensory cortex pain reactivity and decreased the thalamic response (64). On a pathogenetic basis, insufficient sleep quantity has been observed to induce or aggravate pain through the activation of principal inflammatory mediators, such as IL-6 and prostaglandin E2 (65,66) as well as through the involvement of proinflammatory transcription factors, such as nuclear factor- κ B and activator protein 1 that lead to NOD-, LRR- and pyrin domain-containing protein 3 (NLRP3) inflammasome activation (67,68). Furthermore, chronic sleep deprivation has been associated with persistent activation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis. As a result, immune cells may develop NLRP3-mediated glucocorticoid resistance, and thus, facilitate inflammatory processes (69–73). Sleep deprivation and, specifically, REM sleep deprivation increases whole-brain excitatory amino-acid concentrations (e.g., glutamate) (74), which in turn may lead to facilitation of nociceptive transmission via modulation of the descending pain-control pathway (75). In addition, REM sleep deprivation decreases the levels of serotonin and its metabolite (5-HIAA) in the extracellular brainstem of rats (76), where serotonergic cells play an inhibitory role on nociception (77). In similar studies, total sleep deprivation was associated with a decrease in μ and δ opioid receptor binding in the rat limbic system (Fadda 1991), which might explain hyperalgesic responses secondary to an attenuated opioid network. Beyond sleep deprivation, sleep fragmentation is proven to disrupt the normal function of “ON” and “OFF” cells of the periaqueductal gray (PAG) - rostral ventromedial medulla (RVM) pathway

of descending projections. Normally, “ON” cell activity promotes wakefulness and alertness to sensory stimuli, whereas “OFF” cells are active during sleep and attenuate responses to acute painful stimuli. As such, it has been proposed that sleep disruption can lead to “ON” cell activation and “OFF” cell inhibition, thus accentuating pain perception (78). Consequently, the mechanisms described above result in an increased response to nociceptive stimuli.

The above evidence suggests that SRBD pathophysiology to chronic pain is primarily related to sleep fragmentation and deprivation rather than impaired ventilation. They may also suggest that specific SRBD phenotypes are more likely to be associated with pain (e.g., SRBD associated with arousals and sleep deprivation) compared to others (e.g., obesity hypoventilation syndrome). This latter hypothesis is supported based on results from a study modeling pain prediction, where total sleep time was consistently, yet weakly, predictive of pain intensity ($\beta = 0.08$; $p = 0.03$) across models, even if common SRBD metrics were not [7]. In that same study, consistent with popular preconceptions, male sex was the best factor in predicting pain intensity in this population ($\beta = 13.04$; $p = 0.01$) [7], which may be explained by higher μ opioid receptor binding in women than men (79). The above can guide us on treatment considerations at the interface of SRBD and pain, indicating that it is of equal, if not greater, importance to follow on sleep fragmentation and deprivation improvement with therapies beyond simply improving hypoxia-hypercapnia.

Finally, it is worth considering that SRBD mechanisms of hypoxia-hypercapnia or sleep deprivation and fragmentation may indirectly be associated with pain by provoking other painful conditions. For example, in people with sickle cell disease, hypoxia may lead acutely to a sickle cell crisis and, thus, pain (80). Similarly, long-term sleep deprivation has been associated with increased risk for cancer (81), which may eventually be associated with increased pain. In the same vein, commonly observed comorbid sleep disorders to SRBD are associated with increased pain. This is especially true for insomnia that coexists with SRBD 16% – 75% across studies and further increases pain intensity, even though

overall pain prevalence does not differ (82,83). This is suggestive of certain people being more susceptible to pain perception with increased burden of homeostatic and circadian dysregulation, rather than there being an additive effect across all people. Deep phenotyping of these individuals may provide further insight into how we can identify people-at-risk, as well as novel therapeutic avenues for pain management beyond sleep and circadian consolidation.

Treatment considerations at the interface of SRBD and Pain Syndromes

A body of evidence supports treatment of SRBD in improving pain syndromes, since one-in-seven to one-in-three people who have SRBD also have pain symptoms or a pain disorder (**Table 1**) and since SRBD treatments have proven beneficial for pain outcomes. The first line treatment for SRBD, PAP/NIV therapy, has been proven beneficial in improving different pain syndromes and features. In people with OSA and morning headaches, 60.4% - 81.3% achieve headache resolution with PAP treatment (12). Treatment effectiveness increases cumulatively over time, where in a study of 156 patients with morning headache, 72.4% had symptom resolution after a day, 84.2% at the end of the first week, and 92.1% at the end of the first month of treatment (6). PAP therapy has also been proven effective in improving pain tolerance for people older than 70 years old on an electrical pain tolerance score, but only when treatment between 5-10 cmH₂O, rather than 4 cmH₂O PAP, was pursued (84). Although evidence for patients with CWP undergoing SRBD treatment is meagre, a study revealed that after a three-week nasal PAP treatment, 38% of women with CWP demonstrated an improvement in pain symptoms (85). The above inform clinicians of achieving a minimum therapeutic pressure target, as well as encouraging their patients of prolonged compliance in order to observe benefits in pain symptoms in addition to SRBD symptoms.

The opposite effect, however, has been observed in people pursuing mandibular advancement device (MAD) therapy for OSA. In a study of 40 people with OSA treated with MAD, 20 had to stop treatment

over five years. Of those who stopped, 17.6% discontinued use shortly after initiation because of newly developed pain, and reached 20% at five years. (86). Additionally, of an additional 10 patients who had TMD at baseline prior to therapy and, nonetheless, pursued MAD therapy, only one continued to use a MAD at 58 months. The above are further supported by a study where MAD use compared to PAP therapy resulted in greater temporomandibular pain and pain-related TMDs (odds ratio 2.33, 95% confidence interval 1.22-4.43) (87). Even though these results indicate that MAD use is associated with new or worsened pain, considering that pain symptoms predominantly emerge during the initial therapy period, it is reasonable for clinicians to follow up for side-effects shortly after treatment initiation and advise patients accordingly if alternative treatments should be considered. Whether the emerging pain from MAD persists after its discontinuation, has not been studied.

With regards to surgical interventions for SRBD, there is inherent pain associated with the procedures themselves, especially soft tissue procedures, which are also more common in children. The most common first line treatment for SRBD in children is tonsillectomy. Of the different techniques, extracapsular tonsillectomy is seven times more likely to cause postoperative pain and hemorrhage compared to intracapsular tonsillectomy, although the prevalence is overall small (2.1% vs 0.3%; $p = 0.025$) (88). With the immediate post-operative benefit on SRBD outcomes not being different between the two methods across studies for both adults and in children (89,90), it is reasonable to consider the less painful procedure. Nonetheless, it is more likely for tonsils to re-grow in pre-adolescent children after intracapsular interventions, with revision surgery being pursued from 0.3% at 1 year to 2.2% at 5 years within the National Healthcare System of the United Kingdom (91), suggesting that the medical need for revision surgery due to suboptimal outcomes is likely larger. Beyond tonsillectomy, a study on 48 people with OSA identified that tongue base suspension was associated with more pain and need for rescue analgesics compared to lateral pharyngoplasty (73.3% vs. 16.7%). The least painful outcomes,

however, were observed in patients who underwent anterior palatoplasty, had less pain, and did not require any rescue analgesics (92).

The evidence presented above informs the clinician on how to account for pain comorbidity in treatment decisions for SRBD. Specifically, PAP/NIV therapy is an effective first line treatment in adults for both SRBD and pain attenuation, whereas MAD use should be closely monitored, if not avoided, in people at high risk for TMD and other pain. If an adult patient chooses to undergo soft tissue surgery for SRBD, anterior palatoplasty is associated with less pain, yet, as with all surgeries, success is considered as an improvement of SRBD metrics by more than 50%, rather than complete resolution. For children, intracapsular tonsillectomy is less painful, yet with non-negligible chances of tonsillar re-growth, requiring this information during discussions with children and parents for informed decision making.

Conclusions and Future Directions

In summary, people with SRBD are three to four times more likely to satisfy criteria for one of TTH, morning headache, CWP, or TMD syndromes, highlighting the need to inquire for these in clinical practice, especially since PAP/NIV therapy improves pain symptoms. Treatment response depends on the specific pain syndrome, and ranges from 38% in CWP to 92% in morning headaches. For optimal therapeutic benefits, treating physicians should make efforts to achieve a minimum therapeutic pressure target, as well as to encourage prolonged PAP/NIV compliance.

The two main mechanisms explaining how SRBD may lead to pain are (a) SRBD-associated hypoxia-hypercapnia, which likely exacerbates pain acutely, but may allow for decreased responsiveness to pain in the long term, and (b) sleep fragmentation and deprivation, which seems to contribute even more to chronic pain. As such, the clinician should consider that SRBD phenotypes associated with arousals and sleep deprivation, rather than, for example, obesity hypoventilation, are more likely to be accompanied

by pain, and that therapeutic targets of minimizing arousals should be considered when assessing treatment success.

The inverse relationship, where presence of a pain syndrome increases the chance of SRBD has not been observed in case-control studies. That said, the higher prevalence of RERA in TMD, indicative of more effortful breathing, informs clinicians that polysomnography studies that include electroencephalography for arousal measurements should be performed when assessing SRBD in TMD. Another finding that contrasts a common assumption is that in people who are using opioids have more severe obstructive apnea events than central events. Even more, in most people with chronic pain and opioid use, central apneas are not more frequent than in the general population; possibly because of below-threshold opioid dosing practices. These findings suggest that, in clinical practice, conventional treatment with PAP/NIV rather than servo-ventilation can be pursued for most patients.

The above can direct clinical practice by improving deep phenotyping of sleep clinic patients and help develop optimal cost-effective interdisciplinary diagnostic algorithms. They also inform future research in pursuing novel therapeutic avenues for pain management across SRBD-associated mechanisms of hypoxia-hypercapnia and sleep fragmentation and deprivation.

Ethics Declarations

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Table 1. SRBD associations to Pain Syndromes

Study	Precondition Syndrome	Outcome Syndrome	Population	Study Design	Result
Alberti et al. 2005 (62)	OSA (PSG-based)	Headache (ICHD-II criteria)	Age 52.4 ± 12.7 N = 56 (49 men, 7 women)	Cohort	Prevalence 48.2% (70.4% on awakening)
Beiske et al. 2013 (93)	OSA (PSG-based)	Headache (Qs)	Age 55.1 ± 12.9 N = 477 (61% men, 39% women) N _{OSA} = 252 N _{NO OSA} = 225	Cohort referred for sleep study Case-control	Prevalence 77-84% (OSA across HA frequency) - Mild: 84% - Moderate: 80% - Severe: 77% vs. 87% (No OSA across HA frequency); p=NS
Goksan et al. 2009 (6)	OSA (PSG-based)	Morning headache (ICHD & IHS criteria)	Age 22 – 84 N _{AHI>5} = 462 N _{AHI<5} = 101	Cross-sectional	Prevalence 33.6% (OSA) - Severe: 38.4% - Moderate: 36.8% - Mild: 22% vs. 8.9% (no-OSA); p<0.001
Aldrich & Chauncey 1990 (7)	SAS (PSG-based)	Frequent morning headaches (Qs)	Age unspecified N _{SAS} = 304 (241 men, 63 women) N _{Other-SRBD} = 24 N _{Controls} = 65	Cross-sectional	Prevalence 18% (SAS) [20% in OSA vs. 13% in CSA/mixed] vs. 33% (Other-SRBD) vs. 6% (Control); p=0.0008
Suzuki et al. 2015 (12)	OSA on CPAP (PSG-based)	Morning headache (ICHD-II criteria) / Sleep apnea headache subtype	Age 54.8 ± 11.6 N = 235	Cross-sectional Retrospective medical record	Prevalence morning headache 20.4%: - 25% migraine - 39.6% TTH

		(ICHD-II criteria, ICHD-III criteria)	(190 men, 45 women)	review prior to CPAP initiation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2.1% cluster headache - 33.3% others <p>Sleep apnea headache</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 60.4% of morning headaches (ICHD-II) - 81.3% of morning headaches (ICHD-III)
Doufas et al. 2013 (8)	Nocturnal hypoxemia (PSG-based)	Morning headache / Headache disrupting sleep / Chest pain while in bed (Qs)	<p>Age 16 – 89</p> <p>N_{MH} = 576</p> <p>N_{HDS} = 561</p> <p>N_{CPWIB} = 562</p>	Cross-sectional	<p>Adjusted OR morning headache 1.36 (1.08 - 1.71)</p> <p>Adjusted OR headache disrupting sleep 1.29 (1.10 - 1.51)</p> <p>Adjusted OR chest pain while in bed 1.37 (1.10 – 1.70)</p>
Göder et al. 2003 (9)	SAS (PSG-based)	Morning TTH (Diagnostic criteria of IHS, Qs)	<p>Age_{SAS} 18 – 86</p> <p>Age_{Controls} 24 – 55</p> <p>N_{SAS} = 152 (63% men, 37% women)</p> <p>N_{Controls} = 30 (73% men, 27% women)</p>	Prospective case-control	<p>Prevalence of headache in the past 27% (SAS) vs. 7% (Control); p<0.05</p> <p>Prevalence of headache during sleep study 22% (SAS) vs. 3% (Control); p<0.05</p>
Chiu et al. 2015 (10)	OSA (PSG-based)	TTH (ICD-9 codes)	<p>Age ≥ 18</p> <p>N_{OSA} = 4,759 (3,378 men, 1,381 women)</p> <p>N_{Controls} = 19,036</p>	Case-control	<p>Prevalence 10.2% (OSA) vs. 7.7% (Control); p<0.001</p> <p>Incidence 3.7% / yr (OSA) vs. 2.8% / yr (Control);</p>

			(13,512 men, 5,524 women; without OSA diagnosis in medical records)		p<0.001 Adjusted HR 1.18 (1.06-1.31); p=0.003
Kristiansen et al. 2011 (11)	OSA (PSG-based)	Frequent and chronic TTH (ICHD criteria)	Age 30 – 65 Stratified selection from N _{high risk OSA} = 297 N _{low risk OSA} = 134	Cross-sectional selection via Qs for OSA symptoms from population with subsequent PSG	Adjusted OR frequent TTH 0.95 (0.55 – 1.62) Adjusted OR chronic TTH 1.91 (0.37 – 9.85)
Kristiansen et al. 2011 (15)	OSA (PSG-based)	Migraine with and without aura (ICHD criteria)	Age 30 – 65 Stratified selection from N _{high risk OSA} = 376 N _{low risk OSA} = 157	Cross-sectional selection via Qs for OSA symptoms from population with subsequent PSG	Adjusted OR with aura 1.15 (0.65–2.06) Adjusted OR without aura 1.15 (0.95–2.39)
Martinez-Gomis et al. 2010 (86)	OSA (PSG-based)	TMD (Research diagnostic criteria)	Age 35 – 70 N = 40	Cross-sectional	Prevalence 25%
Sanders et al. 2013 (94)	SAS (Self-report and presumed from Qs)	TMD (Research diagnostic criteria)	Age 18 – 44 N = 2,604	Prospective cohort 2.8-year f/u	Adjusted HR 1.73 (1.14-2.62)
Bonetti et al. 2021 (13)	Untreated OSA (PSG-based)	TMD (Research diagnostic criteria)	Age _{OSA} 49.7 + 10.5 Age _{Controls} 50.3+15.4	Case-control	Prevalence 51% (OSA) vs. 32% (Control); p<0.05

			<p>$N_{OSA} = 41$ (31 men, 10 women) $N_{Controls} = 41$ (31 men, 10 women)</p>		
Sanders et al. 2013 (94)	SAS (Self-report and presumed from Qs)	TMD (Research diagnostic criteria)	<p>Age 18 – 44</p> <p>$N_{TMD} = 182$ $N_{Controls} = 1,534$</p>	Cross-sectional case-control	Adjusted OR 3.63 (2.03-6.52)
Aytekin et al. 2015 (95)	OSA (PSG-based)	Chronic widespread musculoskeletal pain (ACR Diagnostic criteria)	<p>Age 39 - 63</p> <p>$N = 74$ (44 men, 30 women)</p>	Cross-sectional	<p>Prevalence CWP 55.4%</p> <p>Higher incidence of CWP in women (56% of all CWP patients)</p> <p>No correlation between degree of sleep disorder and severity of pain</p>
Yildirim & Alp 2017 (96)	OSA (PSG-based)	Fibromyalgia (ACR Diagnostic criteria)	<p>Age 48.8 ± 8.8</p> <p>$N_{OSA} = 131$ $N_{OSA \text{ w/ FMS}} = 50$ $N_{OSA \text{ w/o FMS}} = 81$</p>	Case-control Cohort	<p>Prevalence w/ FMS vs. w/o FMS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 34% vs. 37% (Mild OSA) - 12% vs. 16% (Moderate OSA) - 54% vs. 46.9% (Severe OSA); <p>$p=0.831$</p> <p>Correlation AHI-FIQ -0.184; $p=0.206$</p>
Pejovic et al. 2015 (14)	SAS (PSG-based)	Fibromyalgia (1990 ACR Diagnostic criteria) / Chronic fatigue syndrome (1994 CDC Fukuda)	<p>Age > 18</p> <p>$N_{SAS} = 122$ (83 men, 39 women) $N_{Controls} = 39$ (17 men, 22 women)</p>	Cohort Case-control	<p>Prevalence fibromyalgia 3% (SAS) vs. 0% (Control); $p=0.065$</p> <p>Prevalence chronic fatigue syndrome 13% (SAS) vs. 0% (Control); $p=0.001$</p>
Suen et al. 2021 (17)	OSA on CPAP	Post-operative pain control	<p>Age_{adherent} 51 ± 11</p>	Cross-sectional	Prevalence inadequate pain control 11.4% (Adherent) vs.

	(PSG / HST-based)	(Visual Analogue Scale)	Age _{Non-adherent} 51 ± 15 N _{adherent} = 76 (23 men, 53 women) N _{Non-adherent} = 56 (22 men, 34 women)		25.9% (Non-adherent); p= 0.03
Strutz et al. 2019 (97)	OSA (STOP-Bang score)	Postoperative pain (Visual Analogue Scale)	Age 68.8 ± 9.5 N = 1,441 N _{LowRiskOSA} = 268 (44 men, 224 women) N _{IntermediateRiskOSA} = 580 (309 men, 271 women) N _{HighRiskOSA} = 593 (421 men, 172 women)	Retrospective cohort	No significant difference in maximum pain reported between groups High- vs. Low- Risk Groups Adjusted OR 1.34 (0.80 -2.23) Intermediate- vs. Low- Risk Groups Adjusted OR 0.85 (0.54 – 1.33)
Liu et al. 2022 (98)	OSA (PSG-based)	Pain (Qs)	Age 18 – 80 N = 145	Cross-sectional	Prevalence 37.9%
Smith et al. 2009 (99)	SAS (PSG-based) in TMD	Pain sensitivity (Algometric measures)	Age 33.6 ± 12.4 N = 15 (5 men, 10 women)	Cross- sectional	Increased pressure pain threshold (hypoalgesia) on the forearm (RDI β=0.25; p=0.04) Trend toward hypoalgesia at the masseter site (RDI β=0.18, p=0.19)
Athar et al. 2020 (18)	OSA (ICD-9 codes)	Moderate / Severe pain intensity (NRS)	Age 27 – 42 N = 91,244	Cross-sectional	Adjusted OR 1.09 (1.08 – 1.11)
Silva et al. 2018 (100)	OSA in early grade OA	Pain/ Stiffness	Age 40 – 70	Cross-sectional	People with OA and OSA had more pain and stiffness compared to

	(PSG-based)	(WOMAC questionnaire)	N = 60 (all men) N _{G1} = 15 (Control) N _{G2} = 15 (with OA & without OSA) N _{G3} = 15 (without OA & with OSA) N _{G4} = 15 (with OA and with OSA)		control group or people with OSA but without OA
Terzi & Yilmaz 2015 (19)	OSA (PSG-based)	Pressure-pain threshold (Myalgic score [pain tolerance])	Age 18 – 45 all women N _{OSA} = 31 N _{Controls} = 31	Case-control	Pain Threshold 73.95 ± 18.09 (OSA) vs. 84.18 ± 24.31 (Control); p=0.041 Number of tender points 8.19 ± 3.35 (OSA) vs. 6.35 ± 2.23 (Control); p=0.014
Rhodes et al. 2020 (101)	High risk for OSA (Symptoms, Qs)	Pain during physical activity (Qs)	Age 53.8 ± 12.4 N = 60 (35 men, 25 women)	Cross-sectional Cohort	Prevalence 55%
Chung et al. 2014 (102)	OSA (PSG-based)	Bladder Pain / Interstitial Cystitis (ICD-9 codes)	Age > 18 stratified by decade N _{OSA} = 2,940 N _{Controls} = 29,400	Retrospective Cohort 3-year f/u	Incidence (%) 13.61 (7.37–23.13) vs. 3.60 (2.06–4.39); p unspecified Adjusted HR 3.71 (1.81–7.62); p<0.001
Hrubos-Strøm et al. 2012 (16)	OSA (PSG-based)	Somatoform pain disorder (DSM-IV)	Age 30 – 65 N _{OSA} = 175	Case-control	Prevalence 16.6% (OSA) vs. 23.7% (Control);

			N _{Controls} = 115		p=0.135 OR Women : Men 4.15 (2.19 – 7.85)
<p>ACR: American College of Rheumatology; CI: Confidence interval 95%; CPAP: Continuous positive airway pressure; CPWIB: Chest Pain while in bed; CSA: Central Sleep Apnea; DSM: Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders; f/u: follow-up; G: Group; HA: Headache; HDS: Headache Disrupting Sleep; HR: Hazard Ratio; HST: Home Sleep Test; ICHD: International Classification of Headache Disorders; IHS: International Headache Society; MH: Morning Headache; NRS: Numeric Rating Scale; NS: Non-significant; OA: Osteoarthritis; OR: Odds Ratio; OSA: Obstructive Sleep Apnea; PSG: Polysomnography; Qs: Questionnaires; SAS: Sleep Apnea Syndrome; TMD: Temporomandibular Disorder; TTH: Tension type headache; WOMAC: Western Ontario McMaster Osteoarthritis Index</p>					

Table 2. Pain Syndromes associations to SRBD

Study	Precondition Syndrome	Outcome Syndrome	Population	Study Design	Result
Lovati et al. 2011 (20)	Headache (ICHD-II criteria)	OSA (HST-based)	Age 59.4 ± 13.1 N _{Headache} = 69 N _{Controls} = 112	Case-control	AHI 15.3% (Headache) vs. 26.3% (Control); p=8x10 ⁻⁴ %time SpO ₂ <90% 6.5 (Headache) vs. 16.2 (Control); p=8x10 ⁻³
Vendrame et al. 2008 (27)	Headache (ICHD-II criteria for children)	OSA and UARS (PSG-based)	Age 5 – 19 (Mean 11 y.o) N = 90 (54 boys, 36 girls)	Cross-sectional Cohort	Prevalence 49% (SRBD) - UARS 33.5% - OSA 15.5% Prevalence per type - Migraine 56.6% - Chronic migraine 27% - Nonspecific 54% - TTH 0%

Pavone et al. 2012 (103)	Headache (ICHD-II criteria)	OSA (Qs-based)	Age 4 – 14 $N_{\text{Headache}} = 280$ $N_{\text{Controls}} = 280$	Case-Control	Incidence (%) 3.2 (Headache) vs. 5.5 (Control); $p=0.2$
Graff-Radford & Newman 2004 (104)	Cluster Headache (IHS criteria)	OSA (PSG-based)	Age 33 – 78 $N = 31$	Case series	Prevalence $AHI \geq 5$ 80.64%
Barloese et al. 2015 (23)	Cluster Headache (ICHD-II criteria)	SAS (PSG-based)	Age _{CH} 44.2 ± 11.2 Age _{Controls} 47.6 ± 12.1 $N_{\text{CH}} = 40$ (29 men, 11 women) $N_{\text{Controls}} = 25$ (16 men, 9 women)	Case-control	Prevalence 38% (CH) vs. 32% (Controls); $p=0.64$
Mitsikostas et al. 2007 (105)	Refractory chronic headache (>15 d/month ≥ 6 months)	OSA (PSG-based)	Age 56.6 ± 8.1 (21 men, 51 women) $N = 72$	Cohort	Prevalence OSA 29.2% (13.7% of women, 66.6% of men)
Domany et al. 2019 (26)	Migraine (ICHD criteria)	SAS (PSG-based)	Age _{Migraine} 13.5 ± 3.4 $N_{\text{Migraine}} = 185$ (39% boys, 61% girls)	Retrospective cohort	Prevalence OSA 40% - Mild 29% - Moderate/ Severe 11% Prevalence CSA 0.5% Mean AHI 2.4 ± 2.05

Buse & Rains 2019 (106)	Migraine (Web-based Qs; ICHD-III criteria)	SAS (Berlin Q, self-report)	Age 41.3 ± 14.5 N = 12,810 N _{EM} = 11,699 (3,015 men, 8,684 women) N _{CM} = 1,111 (205 men, 906 women)	Cross-sectional	Berlin Q high risk for SAS 37% (Total) 51.8% (EM) vs. 35.6% (CM); p<0.001 Self-report of SAS 10.1% (Total) 14.1% (EM) vs. 9.7% (CM); p<0.001
Smith et al. 2009 (99)	TMD (Research diagnostic criteria)	SAS (PSG-based)	Age 33.6 ± 12.4 N = 53 (43 women, 10 men)	Cross-sectional Cohort	Prevalence 28.4% - Mild OSA 20.8% - Moderate OSA 3.8% - Severe OSA 3.8%
Dubrovsky et al. 2014 (21)	TMD with myofascial pain (Research diagnostic criteria)	Sleep fragmentation / RERA events (PSG-based)	Age 19 – 78 (Mean 39.2 yo; all women) N _{TMD} = 124 N _{Controls} = 46	Case-Control	AHI 3.7 ± 6.6 (TMD) vs. 2.4 ± 3.9 (Control); p=0.5 RERA index 4.3 ± 4.3 (TMD) vs. 2.6 ± 2.7 (Control); p=0.02 Arousal index 18.2 ± 11.3 (TMD) vs. 14.3 ± 7.8 (Controls); p=0.07
Prados et al. 2013 (29)	Fibromyalgia (ACR Diagnostic criteria)	SRBD (PSG-based)	Age 48 ± 8.45 N = 40 (18 men, 22 women)	Cross-sectional	Prevalence of AHI>15 Men 61% vs. Women 31.8%; p<0.05

Mutlu et al. 2020 (30)	Fibromyalgia (ACR Diagnostic criteria)	OSA (Berlin Q, PSG-based)	Age 40 – 68 (52.4 ± 8.0) N = 38 (women)	Cross-sectional	Prevalence AHI≥ 5 65.9% - Severe 21.1% - Moderate 23.7% - Mild 21.1% High risk 36.8% Low risk 63.2%
Jungquist et al. 2012 (22)	Chronic pain (Qs)	OSA or CSA (PSG-based)	Age > 21 N _{No pain} = 171 N _{CP no opioids} = 187 N _{CP opioids} = 61	Case-Control	Prevalence AHI≥5 82.9% (CP _{no opioids}) vs. 77% (CP _{opioids}) vs. 85.4% (No pain); p=NS Mean CAI 1.1 (CP _{no opioids}) vs. 5.0 (CP _{opioids}) vs. 1.6 (No pain); p<0.001
Larsen et al. 2022 (107)	Chronic pain (Self report)	OSA (RP confirmed by PSG)	Age 47.1 ± 11.0 N = 90 (19 men, 71 women)	Cohort	Prevalence OSA 51.1% AHI>15 31.1%
ACR: American College of Rheumatology; AHI: Apnea-Hypopnea Index; CAI: Central Apnea Index; CH: Cluster Headache; CI: Confidence interval 95%; CM: Chronic Migraine; ; CSA: Central Sleep Apnea; EM: Episodic Migraine; HST: Home Sleep Test; ICHD: International Classification of Headache Disorders; NS: Non-significant; OSA: Obstructive Sleep Apnea; PSG: Polysomnography; RERA: Respiratory effort related arousal; RP: Respiratory Polygraphy; SAS: Sleep Apnea Syndrome; TMD: Temporomandibular Disorder; Q(s): Questionnaire(s)					

Table 3: Associations between interventions for Pain Syndromes and SRBD

Study	Precondition Syndrome	Outcome Syndrome	Population	Study Design	Result
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Mogri et al. 2009 (32)	Chronic pain on opioid therapy (Daily use for ≥6 months)	OSA (PSG-based)	Age 22 – 80 (Mean 48 yo) N = 98 (Men:Women = 1.39)	Retrospective case series	Prevalence OSA 36% CSA 24% OSA & CSA 21% No apnea 15% Hypoxemia without apnea 8%
Webster et al. 2008 (34)	Chronic pain on opioid therapy (Daily use for ≥6 months)	OSA or CSA (PSG-based)	Age 22 - 84 (Mean 51 yo) N = 140 (Women:Men = 1.51)	Cross-sectional	Prevalence AHI ≥ 5 75% OSA 39% CSA 24% OSA & CSA 8% (effect mediated by methadone use p=0.007 for OSA and p=0.004 for CSA)
Walker et al. 2007 (108)	Chronic pain on opioid therapy (≥6 months)	SAS (PSG-based)	Age _{Opioids} 52.7 ± 13.1 Age _{No Opioids} 52.9 ± 13.0 N _{Opioids} = 60 (20 men, 40 women) N _{No Opioids} = 60 (20 men, 40 women)	Retrospective Case-control	CAI 12.8 ± 22.4 (Opioids) vs. 2.1 ± 4.1 (No Opioids); p<0.01 OAI 16.8 ± 24.0 (Opioids) vs. 14.2 ± 18.8 (No Opioids); p= 0.508 HI 15.3 ± 14.1 (Opioids) vs. 13.7 ± 13.0 (No Opioids); p=0.466 AHI 43.5 (Opioids) vs 30.2 (No Opioids); p<0.05
Mir et al. 2020 (109)	Chronic non-cancer pain on	SAS (PSG-based)	Age _{OpioidsOnly} 52.7 ± 13.4 Age _{Opioids+CAD}	Prospective cohort study	AHI (Opioids vs. Opioids+CAD) 8 (3.2–17.8) vs. 5.3 (1.5–19.4); p=NS

	opioid therapy ± CAD therapy (>3 months)		51.7 ± 12.9 N = 204 N _{OpioidsOnly} = 71 (32 men, 39 women) N _{Opioids+CAD} 133 (52 men, 81 women)		OAI 5.6 (2.0–12.9) (Opioids) vs. 4.2 (1.3–14.2) (Opioids+CAD); p=NS CAI 0.4 (0–1.7) (Opioids) vs. 0.4 (0–2.6) (Opioids+CAD); p=NS
Tentindo et al. 2018 (110)	Chronic pain with & without opioid therapy (Self report)	SAS (STOP-Bang score ≥ 3)	Age 57.5 ± 13.9 N = 297 (99 men, 193 women, 5 not known) N _{Opioids} = 196 N _{No Opioids} = 101	Cohort Case-control	Prevalence 58.3% (Total) 59.2% (Opioids) vs. 56.4% (No opioids); p=0.82
Pampati & Manchikanti 2016 (33)	Chronic spinal pain (> 1 year) on chronic opioid therapy	OSA (Qs ± PSG)	Age > 18 N = 4,036 (2,314 women, 1,722 men)	Retrospective cohort	Prevalence 13.8% (Women 15.1% vs. Men 12.8%) - >45 y.o 16.3% vs. - 25-45 y.o 10.7% vs. - 18-25 y.o 2.5%
Webster et al. 2015 (37)	Chronic low back pain (≥3 months) on hydromorphone extended- release therapy	SRBD (PSG-based)	Age 44.4 ± 14 N = 15 (6 men, 9 women)	Randomized, double-blind, placebo controlled, crossover	AHI 12.9 (12.8) (QAM) vs. 17.1 (15.6) (QPM); p>0.05 CAI 2.2 (2.6) (QAM) vs. 1.8 (1.6) (QPM); p>0.05 LSatO ₂

					86.0 (4.1) (QAM) vs. 84.6 (7.3) (QPM); p>0.05
<p>AHI: Apnea-Hypopnea Index; CAD: Centrally acting drugs; CAI: Central Apnea Index; CI: Confidence interval 95%; CSA: Central Sleep Apnea; HI: Hypopnea Index; MMT: Methadone Maintenance Treatment; NS: Non-significant; OAI: Obstructive Apnea Index; OSA: Obstructive Sleep Apnea; OSAHI: Obstructive Sleep Apnea-Hypopnea Index; PSG: Polysomnography; SA: Standard agents; SAA: Short-acting agents; SAS: Sleep Apnea Syndrome; QAM: Quaque die ante meridiem; QPM: Quaque die post meridiem; Qs: Questionnaires</p>					

Figure Legends

Figure 1. The Pain Matrix in the multimodal pain perception of pain at the interface between Sleep Disorders and Chronic Pain

The Pain Matrix is a functional network involving clusters of somatosensory, cognitive, and emotional integration, including pain information processing. A forward flow of information from somesthesia to cognitive and emotion networks is combined with feedback pathways within and between the three Pain Matrix clusters, optimizing pain information consolidation. In chronic pain syndromes, central sensitization to pain differentially accentuates pain perception processing within and between clusters. Although a bidirectional relationship between chronic pain and sleep disorders exists for insomnia and sleep deprivation, in the case of SRBD and pain, causality primarily leads from SRBD to chronic pain and not the other way round. See text for details. This figure was adapted from (2) Doufas AG & Karageorgiou E. Sleep and Pain. In: Kryger MH, Roth T, Goldstein CA, editors. Principles and Practice of Sleep Medicine. 7th ed. Elsevier; 2022.

Figure 2. Main pathogenic pathways leading to pain from SRBD

The two main mechanisms that SRBD leads to pain are Hypoxia – Hypercapnia (blue arrows) and Sleep fragmentation / deprivation (yellow arrows). Each has unique downstream pathways, as well as overlapping pathways (green arrows). A common theme for both is the involvement of inflammatory pathways, either directly or indirectly via sympathetic hyperactivity. Of the two mechanisms, sleep fragmentation / deprivation has the strongest association to chronic pain, engaging pathways of hypervigilance and systemic hyperactivity. Common end-node across pathways is central and peripheral sensitization. *Abbreviations: AP-1: Activator protein 1, HIF-1: Hypoxia-inducible factor-1, HPA axis:*

Hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal axis, ICP: Intracranial Pressure, NF-κB: Nuclear factor-κB, NLRP3: NOD-, LRR- and pyrin domain-containing protein 3, PAG - RVM: Periaqueductal Gray - Rostral Ventromedial Medulla, ROS: Reactive Oxygen Species, SRBD: Sleep related breathing disorders, TRPA1: Transient receptor potential cation channel, subfamily A, member 1, TRPV1: Transient receptor potential cation channel subfamily V, member 1, TRPV2: Transient receptor potential cation channel subfamily V, member 2

Figure 1

Figure 2

